

ISic1111

I.Sicily inscription 1111

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Calatafimi, Biblioteca comunale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἱερ[οθ]υτέοντος Φάωνος
2. Νύ[μ][φ]ωνος Σωπολιανοῦ,
3. ἀγορανομέοντος Ξενάρχου
4. Ἀπολλ[οδώ]ρου καὶ τὰν ἐπιμέλειαν
5. πο[ι][η]σαμ]ένου τῶν ἔργων vacat
6. ἀ ῥ[γ][ο][ρ][ᾶ] κατεσκευάσθη

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo and Erdas 2019

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492727

EDCS 39102268

PHI 140594

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1111. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351535>